

A Study to Determine the Correlation between Performance and Structural Empowerment among Staff Nurses in Selected Hospital at Puducherry

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ABSTRACT

Background: Staff nurses account for a significant part of manpower expenditure in the hospitals. They also present serious problems for the hospital management in terms of motivation, absenteeism and turnover. Employee job performance is the fulfillment, gratification, and enjoyment that come from work. It is not just the money or the fringe benefits, but the feelings. The hospital practice environment has a significant impact on nursing job satisfaction and patient outcomes. Every day nurses are challenged to do more with less, require completing more paperwork and charting and job satisfaction is threatened. Often time's organizational change is introduced and implemented without consulting nurses causing friction among the organization and nursing personnel.

Objectives: 1.To assess the performance of staff nurses. 2. To assess the structural empowerment among staff nurses 3. To determine the correlation between performance and structural empowerment among staff nurses. 4. To associate the performance and structural empowerment among staff nurses with the selected demographic variables. Method: A quantitative research approach was adopted. 50 nurses in selected hospital at Puducherry were selected for the study by using purposive sampling technique. Data was collected by using performance appraisal rating scale and checklist questionnaires for structural empowerment.

Result: The study reveals that out of 100% of nurses 20% has excellent performance, 74% has good and 6% poor performance. The study reveals out of 100% of nurses 22% has excellent structural empowerment, 74% has good structural empowerment, 4% has poor structural empowerment. The result shows the correlation value $r = 0.715$. Which lies as the $0 < r < 1$ which indicates that there is moderately positive correlation between the performance and structural empowerment.

Conclusion: The study concluded that there is moderately positive correlation between the performance and structural empowerment among the staff nurse.

Keywords: Structural Empowerment, Staff Nurses.

INTRODUCTION

"Authentic empowerment is the knowing that you are on purpose, doing God's work, peacefully and harmoniously."

Wayne Dye

Staff nurses account for a significant part of manpower expenditure in the hospitals. They also present serious problems for the hospital management in

terms of motivation, absenteeism and turnover. Employee job performance is the fulfillment, gratification, and enjoyment that comes from work. It is not just the money or the fringe benefits, but the feelings. The hospital practice environment has a significant impact on nursing job satisfaction and patient outcomes.

A hospital's work-related efficiency is directly linked to the efficiency of its nurses. Many medical services provided in a hospital are nursing-based. Nurses can significantly affect not only a hospital's image but also the evaluations of its users. In practice, improving nursing work effectiveness directly relates to increasing a hospital's competitiveness. With regard to performance-based pay systems, factors found to affect organizational performance are perceived compensation justice, motivation, role-conflict, professional identity, and organizational psychological factors also affect organizational performance. Furthermore, organizational culture and climate are related to work effectiveness.

In nursing, empowerment is frequently used to characterize nurses who successfully act within their organizations to deliver effective patient care. Empowerment emerges from interactions among individual, organizational, and socio-cultural factors. Empowerment has a direct impact on nursing work effectiveness, including job satisfaction and work productivity, and is a mediating factor in job characteristics and leadership of managers. A structurally empowered nurse is best equipped to protect patients' rights.

A Magnet organization focuses not just on improving its own performance but also on contributing new knowledge to the science of nursing. It's expected to use the latest research-based evidence in all of its practices. Exemplary professional practice in a Magnet organization transcends the organization itself and extends to the practice of nursing as a whole. One way to transcend the organization is through community outreach. A strong professional nursing practice in a Magnet organization should be palpable in the community. An empowered nurse who's involved in committees and task forces that influence change in the hospital also may serve on community boards. In this way, she or he leaves a nursing imprint on healthcare policies outside the hospital. When hospital

leaders support this nurse's community involvement, they're demonstrating structural empowerment.

Kanter's (1977) theory of structural empowerment is a good framework to explain concepts related to negative workplace behaviors, such as turnover. The structure of the work environment is an important correlate of employee attitude and behaviors in organizations and that perceived access to power and opportunity structures relate to the behaviors and attitudes of employees in organizations. Kanter suggested that individuals display different behaviors depending on whether certain structural supports (power and opportunity) were in place.

The access to empowerment structures is associated with the degree of formal and informal power an individual has in the organization. Formal power is derived from jobs that allow flexibility, visibility, and creativity. Formal power is also derived from jobs that are considered relevant and central to the organization. Informal power is developed from relationships and networks with peers, subordinates, and superiors within and outside of the organization.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

Hospitals are stressful places of employment due to the increased complexity and demands of most job descriptions, the unpredictable changes in one's daily routine, unrealistic expectations from the patients and their families, and common encounters with ethical end of life issues. Of all the various types of hospital employees, nurses are often important member in maintaining the quality of the hospitals and the health care environment. In most countries of the world there is a shortage of nurses, it is acute in developing countries. In India nurses' shortage occurs at every level of the healthcare system. Only 40 per cent of the total nursing workforce in the country is said to be active because of low recruitment, migration, attrition and drop-outs due to poor working conditions.

By the year 2012, 2.4 million nurses will be needed to provide a nurse-patient ratio of 1 per 500 patients.

Performance and empowerment are interrelated, and which can lead to physical, psychosocial problems, decreased productivity and capacity of nurses which in turn have an effect on the patients, because the efficiency, productivity and capacity and health of the nurse will reflect directly on the care she is providing to the patients.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

A study to determine the correlation between performance and structural empowerment among staff nurses selected hospital at Puducherry.

OBJECTIVES:

- To assess the performance of staff nurses and structural empowerment among staff nurses
- To determine the correlation between performance and structural empowerment among staff nurses.
- To associate the performance and structural empowerment among staff nurses with the selected demographic variables.

ASSUMPTION:

It is assumed that:

- There will be excellent performance and structural empowerment among staff nurses.
- There will be positive correlation between the performance and structural empowerment among staff nurses.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research approach: Quantitative approach is selected for this study.

Research design: Descriptive research design.

Study setting

The study was conducted in selected hospital at Puducherry.

Population

The population for the present study comprises of all staff nurses working in selected hospital

Sample

The samples of this present study were the 50 staff nurses.

Sample technique

The sampling technique used is convenient sampling, 50 samples are taken as the subject of the study

DESCRIPTION OF THE TOOL

Development of data collection instrument has 3 sections:

Section I - Demographic Data which comprises of variables like Age, Sex, Educational Qualification, Year of Experience, Monthly Income, Religion, Marital Status, Area of Working.

Section II - performance appraisal rating scale was used to assess the performance of staff nurses.

Section III - checklist questionnaire was used to assess structural empowerment of staff nurses

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

TABLE – I: Frequency distribution and percentage of samples according to the level of performance among staff nurses.

	NUMBER OF SAMPLE	PERCENTAGE
Poor	3	6%
Good	37	74%
Excellent	10	20%

TABLE – I The findings reveals out of 100% of nurses 20% has excellent performance, 74% had good performance and 6% had poor performance.

Figure 1: frequency and percentage distribution of samples according to the level of performance among staff nurses

TABLE – II: Frequency distribution and percentage of samples according to the structural empowerment among staff nurses.

	NUMBER OF SAMPLE	PERCENTAGE
Poor	2	4%
Good	37	74%
excellent	11	22%

TABLE – II: The findings reveals out of 100% of nurses 22% has excellent structural empowerment, 74% had good structural empowerment and 4% had poor structural empowerment.

Figure 2: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of samples according to the Level of Structural Empowerment among staff nurses

MAJOR FINDING OF THE STUDY

- ❖ The study reveals that out of 100% of nurses 20% has excellent performance, 74% has good and 6% poor performance.
- ❖ The study reveals out of 100% of nurses 22% has excellent structural empowerment, 74% has good structural empowerment, 4% has poor structural empowerment
- ❖ In this study the correlation between the performance and structural empowerment among the staff nurse as the result shows the correlation value $r = 0.715$. which lies as the $0 < r < 1$ which indicates that there is moderately positive correlation between the performance and structural empowerment.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that there is moderately positive correlation between the

performance and structural empowerment among the staff nurse.

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